

Simplifying Quadrotor Frame Design: Toward Scalability with a Modular Robot

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Abstract—For aerial manipulation, current multirotor architectures lack modularity due to the integration of numerous components, making them complex, difficult to assemble and to maintain. To address this, we propose a redefined quadrotor frame design within a weight-optimized paradigm. By strategically placing components and utilizing optimization design techniques, we have developed a lightweight robot frame. This design simplifies the assembly process and accommodates various components, reducing the number of parts and, consequently, the risk of failure. Multiple flight tests have demonstrated the reliability of this aerial robot. Additionally, the chassis, along with complementary parts, is shared open-source, promoting accessibility as well as reproducibility and further development within the community.

Index Terms—Telemanipulation, Quadrotor, Aerial Physical Interaction, Generative Design

I. INTRODUCTION

Multirotor systems have gained popularity due to their reduced mechanical complexity compared to helicopters [1]. However, their increased intricacy arises from the integration of multiple sensors for precise state estimation and the addition of manipulators for physical interaction. Typically, multirotors are constructed using Carbon Fiber (CF) sheets and tubes, known for their lightweight properties. However, this advantage is offset by the addition of numerous screws, nuts, and plastic junctions, which contribute to increased total weight, prolonged assembly time, and more challenging maintenance.

In the field of aerial manipulation, multirotor design typically focuses on input allocation [2] or unconventional frame design [3]. However, to the best of the author’s knowledge, no significant research has explored frame design specifically for aerial manipulation tasks. This area of focus is critical, as the frame’s flexibility can lead to unwanted behaviors that affect the robot’s performance [4].

The current research builds upon [5], which presents the controller, with the goal of simplifying quadrotor frame architecture to facilitate ease of scalability and future modifications. Considering the described gaps, our contributions are *i*) the description of the modularity requirement; *ii*) the design of a scalable frame; and *iii*) preliminary flight tests.

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Fig. 1: Teardown of the different parts of the proposed frame.

II. ROBOT PRESENTATION

A. Platform Requirements

The quadrotor model presented in [5] is designed for transporting suspended loads. In such applications, minimizing the frame’s weight is critical since every gram saved on the robot can be reallocated to increase the payload capacity. Achieving this balance requires reducing unnecessary material in the frame while maintaining sufficient resilience against physical interactions. Additionally, the frame must be manufacturable using standard tools like additive printers or Computerized Numerical Control (CNC) cutting machines, ensuring accessibility and cost-effectiveness in production.

B. Robot Design

The proposed robot is presented in Fig. 2. The frame design employs an optimization approach utilizing generative design techniques [6]. This method identifies internal forces on stressed components and precisely positions key elements such as the arm supports, battery, companion computer, flight controller Flight Controller (FC), electronic speed controllers Electric Speed Controller (ESC), and propellers. The approach allows exploration of numerous design configurations while adhering to specific physical and force constraints [7]. The frame dimensions of $210 \times 210 \times 45$ mm are compatible with most standard additive manufacturing machines. Experimentation’s showed PLA to be too fragile at impact, while PETG,

Fig. 2: Mounted brushless motors on the robot arm, with their standardized size (left to right): 2806.5, 2208, 3508, and 2814.

PETG-CF and ABS had great impact resilience. Robot arms are in carbon fiber to diffuse heat, because we noticed printed plastic melting with motors heat. The arms shape is also made universal for most of motors. Finally the arms attach the frame with the flexible TPU landing gears, such that we minimize the number of required nuts.

III. EXPERIMENTAL APPLICATIONS

Extensive flight testing and an iterative development process have provided substantial practical experience. The frame design has been enhanced to increase both strength and modularity. All related components, along with the frame, are openly shared¹.

A. Modularity

In Fig. 2, the arm tip is displayed with different motor footprints, showing the modularity of the design, which allows for the mounting of a wide range of commercially available brushless motors. Also, depending on the use case, various propeller sizes may be necessary. Therefore we propose several arm's length from 7" to 10". The frame can house both LattePanda² and Intel-Up³ companion computers. The open-sourced CAD files can be modified to suit other components.

B. Flight Test Results

Flight test with motors 2806.5 1300kv allowed to lift a heavy 1 kg payload in a cable suspended configuration [5]. Additional flight tests were conducted in a flight arena with a motion capture system. The quadrotor mounted a Pixhawk 6C⁴ and a LattePanda. Small 2208-1400 kv brushless motors with 7" propellers are assembled on the suited arm. Notably, the platform's lightweight frame enables the integration of a companion computer, an addition that would not have been feasible with a typical commercial frame. The tracking performance, obtained using the default controller gains, is illustrated in Fig. 3. The trajectory tracking test yielded promising results, even though the controller gains were not fine-tuned and undersized brushless motors were used relative to the robot's weight. Furthermore, the TPU landing gear demonstrated excellent performance by effectively absorbing multiple rough landings during the experiments, further enhancing the platform's robustness.

¹<https://github.com/jumellet/generative-quadrotor>

²<https://www.lattepanda.com/>

³<https://up-board.org/upsquared/specifications/>

⁴https://docs.px4.io/main/en/flight_controller/pixhawk6c.html

Fig. 3: Plots of the robot freeflight tracking performance. With frames defined in [5], from top to bottom, positions, yaw and differences of reference w.r.t. current.

IV. CONCLUSION

We proposed an open-source quadrotor frame that significantly simplifies robot maintenance by reducing the overall assembly time, thus increasing the platform's operational time in the air. This design approach optimizes the layout and assembly process.

In future work, we aim to formalize the first stage of this design by developing an optimization problem for the spatial positioning of components. The goal will be to align the robot's center of mass with its center of thrust, even with the addition of sensors or a robotic arm manipulator. Additionally, we plan to leverage the simplicity of the design for easier deployment in multi-robot systems.

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